

READING AND READING COMPREHENSION BY A2 STUDENTS

Кодирова Сарвиноз Махмуджон кизи

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ABSTRACT

The article provides information about reading and a brief description of the main types of speech activity. And also highlighted are the levels of reading comprehension, such as literal, analytical and critical understanding, which depends on many factors.

Reading is connected with influence, function, form, action, process and other aspects. Reading is a complex type of speech activity; it has played and continues to play an important role in individual and social life. Research in teaching to read shows that, according to the assessment, reading as a type of speech activity has a long history and shows a number of problems and its approaches.

Contemporary science fiction writer Neil Gaiman noted that "reading is an education that doesn't end the day we leave school or university, it's leisure, it's a refuge, and it's access to information."

In order to develop the ability to understand the content of the text being read, first of all, students should be

introduced to what a book is, what genres of works are, and how to receive information, analyze and comprehend it. Students should become familiar with the fact that books can differ:

- by structure and form: picture books, encyclopedias, panoramic books, mono-editions with one work, collections, including several works or series of books;
- by type of information transfer: paper books, audio books, on-line books, etc.;
- by genre: folk tales, science fiction, fantasy, short stories, poetry, historical works, scientific publications, encyclopedias, journalism, biography/auto-biography, books about art (about music, painting, dancing)[1]. In discussing this

topic, the following stages can be noted when reading:

Before reading - students should be taught to predict, assume, build hypotheses about how the plot of the work will unfold, build guesses that, after reading the text, will be confirmed or refuted. This allows you to track the process of understanding the text: while reading, students will try to find answers to the questions posed before reading, which contributes to a deeper understanding of the text.

During the reading process, the process is organized using different forms of reading: model, collaborative, guided and independent reading (for information on reading forms, see the Introduction and Module 4. Fluent reading).

After reading - students should be taught to find the main information (the hero / characters of the work, what events occurred and what is their sequence, place and time of action), the ability to generalize, compare and contrast the information received from the text, analyze, formulate their opinion and express their attitude to reading, evaluate your reading comprehension. You can also highlight the levels of reading comprehension:

Literal understanding. The first level of understanding lies in the ability to repeat or recreate the text, highlight the main information, identify the main characters, idea, place, time, chronology, plot, action.

analytical understanding. The next level of understanding is the ability to reveal the meaning laid down by the author, to understand cause-and-effect relationships, the ability to analyze and interpret (interpret), compare and contrast familiar and new information.

Critical understanding. And, finally, critical or evaluative understanding is the ability to form and express one's attitude to the text and evaluate one's reading comprehension.

Reading comprehension depends on many factors:

- from understanding the meanings of words;

- from the correctness of reading (if the student reads the words incorrectly, he does not understand the meaning of the whole sentence);

- from fluency (speed) of reading (if the student still reads syllable by syllable, then it is difficult for him/her to "grasp" the meaning of what was read);

- life experience and knowledge of students;

- from the ability to "include" in reading memory, thinking, imagination.

Brief description of the main types of speech activity

There are oral and written speech, each of which has two sides - receptive and expressive speech (Fig. 1) [2].

Rice. 1. The main types of speech activity.

The author Olga Zelinkova defines the term SRSHNN as: „obtíže při osvojování základních školních dovedností – čtení (dyslexie), psaní (dysgrafie, dysortografie), počítání (dyskalkulie) i pohybových dovedností (dyspraxie).

SRRShN are interpreted quite broadly. In the above definition of Zelinkova, not only dyslexia is mentioned, but also other types of disorders - dysgraphia, dysorhography and others.

Dyslexia is a reading disorder. This is the best-known concept of the whole group of specific learning disorders. Initially, the term referred to all types of such violations. Dyslexia can be defined as text-comprehension difficulties characterized by an inability to perceive not only handwritten but also printed text. Dyslexia is characterized by the fact that despite problems with reading, the general level of intelligence of students is at the same level as that of students without specific impairments.

Dysgraphia is a writing disorder. Writing impairment is usually included in the definition of dyslexia. The handwriting of students with dysgraphia is illegible, too small or too large. The shapes of the letters and their connections are usually irregular. It is difficult for students to memorize letters and reproduce them in writing.

Dysorhography is a violation of spelling. This disorder is very often observed simultaneously with dyslexia and dysgraphia. Dysorhography does not concern all areas of grammar, only the so-called specific dysorhographic phenomena. Students with this disorder most often, for example, confuse short and long vowels in the Czech language, do not distinguish between the syllables di-dy, ti-ty, ni-ny. Students with dysorhography add, modify, and omit letters or entire syllables.

The prefix dis- always means warp. In terms of psychological development, dysfunction refers to a function that is not fully developed. Students with dyslexia may also experience speech, concentration, or spatial problems along with SSRS. It is important to note that the slow development of reading, writing and

counting skills in students with a low level of intelligence does not belong to the disorders [3].

Therefore, intermediary activity can easily be associated with non-verbal communication activities, such as verbalization of non-verbal messages.

Reading comprehension typically requires the following skills and knowledge resources:

1. the ability to decipher graphic forms for effective word recognition (phonological, spelling, morphological and semantic processing);

2. the ability to automatically access the meaning of a large number of words (vocabulary);

3. the ability to extract meaning from grammatical information at the level of phrases and sentences (effective grammatical analysis);

4. the ability to combine meanings at the sentence level to create more

a wide network of semantic relations (structuring at the level of discourse and recognition

genres);

5. ability to use different reading strategies with more complex texts

(including goal setting, output and monitoring);

6. ability to draw on life experience, as appropriate;

7. ability to evaluate, integrate and synthesize information from text for

formation of a situational model of understanding (what the reader learns from the text);

8. the ability to freely maintain these processes for a long period
time;

9. ability to continue reading and use textual information appropriately

way in accordance with the purposes of reading [4].

Reading allows you to analyze the degree of perception and acquisition of data in writing.

form. Two types of testing often fall into this class: tests with gaps

(close tests) and texts with all sorts of tasks. Texts with spaces

consider the ability to reconstruct missing significant parts,

maintaining context. In this case, as a rule, the conditions offer short

texts filled with gaps, and these very gaps, the student must fill in, not

forgetting to get to the point.

In tasks, reading becomes more difficult not only in grammatical terms, but there are also

Criteria that help create reinforcing tasks for checking reading. Such

criteria exist for levels A1-C2. We will analyze A1, A2, B1, B2, C1.

For reading characters the following types of tasks [6]:

1. establishing compliance;

2. establishing the sequence of parts of the text;

3. choice from several options only one correct answer;

4. identification;

5. alternative choice;

6. filling in tables or charts;

7. filling in gaps in the text;

8. answers to the given (in the text) questions;

Level A1 is characterized by the following criteria for tasks:

1. No more than 5-10 sentences should be used.

2. The number of words is not more than 20-30.

3. At this level, reinforcing tasks should be no more than 1-2, with a full understanding of the text.

4. Topic, grammar and vocabulary should be familiar.

5. Such reinforcing types of tasks are well suited, such as: choosing from several

options, only one correct answer (no more than 4-6 answer options from the text) or

filling in the gaps (no more than 5-6 gaps from the text), answering questions (no more than 1

question).

Let's show in practice an example of a small text, which is usually shown on

level A1 above the listed criteria (number of words, sentences, simple

grammar and vocabulary):

"I am Jane. I am 18. I am a simple girl who just loves to live. I dream of living on my own when I

grow up. I want to create a strong family and be financially, emotionally independent and strong.»

Level A2 is characterized by the following criteria for tasks:

1. No more than 15-20 sentences should be used

2. The text should not exceed 400-500 words.

3. There can be no more than 2-3 reinforcing tasks at this level.

4. I can read texts with a small amount of unfamiliar vocabulary that does not interfere

general understanding of the text.

5. The following reinforcing types of tasks are suitable: alternative choice (number of

sentences from the general text for reading no more than 10), fill in the gaps in the text

(the number of sentences from the general text is not more than 7-8), establishing correspondence (Not

more than 4-5 matches from the text), answers to questions (no more than 2 questions).

At level A2, the text will be larger in quantity, because the paragraph from level A1 is preserved,

thus, the number of sentences and words for this level fit the criteria.

We will show only a new paragraph (continuation) for this level, the subject of which has not been changed.

The new paragraph contains a small amount of unfamiliar vocabulary and grammar:

"I like that I can spend time with my friends. We often go for a walk together. I can talk to them

for hours. They can not only help me, but also support me in any situation. My mother is a very wise

woman. She always understands me.

As a result, we can say that Reading occupies a significant place in a person's life, starting from the first years of a child's life and ending with mature wisdom. Representatives of various areas of science addressed the study of the problem of reading: teachers (V. A. Sukhomlinsky, K. D. Ushinsky, T. I. Alieva, T. G. Galaktionova, Z. A. Gritsenko, S. V. Evtyushkin, I. G. Zhukova, S. A. Ikramova, O. V. Kiyakina, E. S. Salakhutdinova, N. N. Svetlovskaya, I. P. Smetankina, etc.), psychologists (L. S. Vygotsky, V. V. Davydov, T. G. Egorov, A. A. Leontiev, E. V. Khomskaya, L. S. Tsvetkova, D. B. Elkonin, G. A. Tsukerman, and others), philosophers and sociologists (I. A. Butenko, Yu. A. Eliseeva, E. A. Kolosova, R. A. Trofimova, A. I. Shalimova, etc.), bibliologists and library scientists (V. A. Borodina, S. M. Borodin, O. L. Kabachek, T. A. Novikova, I. I. Tikhomirova, V. P. Chudinova, etc.), etc.).

The philosophical aspect of considering the concept of "reading" is associated with a specific form of linguistic communication of people through printed or handwritten texts, one of the main forms

of mediated communication. Reading differs significantly from other types of communication, which is associated with the specifics of the text as a sign system, the elements of which exist in a fixed spatial form, providing for their subsequent visual perception, and with the possibility of fixing, storing, replicating information in a form in which the consumption processes do not coincide in time with their production, and can last for centuries. This feature turns reading into a very rational way of transferring and assimilating knowledge and values developed by mankind (Ya. Ya. Krasavtseva, V. L. Abushenko, etc.) [7].

The culturological aspect of initiation to reading is considered in the relationship between the reader and the work of art, i.e. the ability of a person to respond to the work being read, to activate their own thoughts and feelings in the course of reading, to recreate images, to leave a trace of what they have read in their soul, to correlate what is read with their experience and knowledge deepen your view of the world.

Laying the responsibility for the intellectual development of society on reading, D.S. Likhachev emphasizes that "the main way of intellectual development is reading. <...> Nothing can replace a book. Despite the latest discoveries, modern ways of preserving information, we will not rush to part with the book. She stays. It is not just read, it is thought about. The new mass media will peacefully coexist with it" [8].

Reading is a system process in which many elements participate. You can't be a good reader without having a culture of reading. Differences in understanding the

culture of reading can be traced in encyclopedic and professional dictionaries and reference books. Experts stopped linking the culture of reading with the general culture of the individual and educational tasks, and turned only to technological aspects. The encyclopedic dictionary "Book" highlights such parameters of the culture of reading as: the ability to navigate in book products, choose literature, apply rational ways of working with text and optimally perceive what is read[9]. In the specialized literature, various phrases with the word "reading" are used - this is the culture of reading, children's reading, etc. V. A. Borodin and S. M. Borodin, A. P. Kashkarov, Z. N. Ovsyankina and others understand the culture of reading "a complex education, it reflects many components of personality development." Among them, the authors distinguish: worldview, information and bibliographic, cultural, philosophical, psychological, literary components, including the development of the speech activity of the individual as a whole. Such polyfunctionality causes objective

difficulties in cultivating a culture of reading in lifelong education [10].

The studies of T. D. Polozova[11] bring together the concepts of "culture of reading", "creative reading", "art of reading": personally significant spiritual, creative activity of each reader, which determines the educational and aesthetic value of literature and reading, a holistic aesthetic perception of what is read - to read and to think, read and feel, transfer the knowledge gained from books to your inner self, to interpersonal relationships.

Thus, reading is a receptive type of activity, which consists in the perception and processing by the reader of an objectively existing text - a product of the reproductive activity of a certain author. In the process of reading, all analyzers responsible for the perception of language and speech are activated: visual as the main, speech-motor and auditory as auxiliary. And the main thing is the time separated for reading and the main thing in it is to learn what you read.

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